

Appendix A: PRISMA 2020 Checklist Application

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review. The title “Large Language Models in the Crosshairs: A Systematic Review of Modern Cybersecurity Challenges and Applications ” identify the report as a systematic review	Title page: 1
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	Abstract page 1	Abstract: 2
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Based on the different perspectives on the use of LLMs in cybersecurity, a fundamental question arises: how can LLMs be integrated into cybersecurity operations in a secure, reliable, and useful way? While several studies have explored the use of LLMs in cybersecurity, most focus on specific applications, such as threat intelligence gathering, phishing detection, or log analysis. Consequently, the existing literature lacks a consolidated and structured understanding of how LLMs are applied across different areas of cybersecurity, the main technical and ethical challenges associated with their integration, and which applications demonstrate the greatest potential for useful and effective use in real-world cybersecurity practice.	Background: 5,6,7
Objectives	4	In this context, the present article presents a systematic literature review that aims to summarize and organize existing research on the application of Large Language Models in cybersecurity. This review identifies the main application areas of LLMs, discusses the most relevant technical and ethical challenges associated with their use, and provides a structured synthesis aligned with the research questions addressing application domains, integration challenges, and the most useful and relevant uses of LLMs in professional cybersecurity environments.	why this review is important, objectives: 7,8
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses. The inclusion criteria focused on studies addressing relevant information about LLM applications in cybersecurity, while non-relevant, non-English or Spanish, or pre-2020 studies were excluded. In addition, grey literature (e.g., preprints and technical/industrial reports) was considered when directly relevant to the research questions and when it passed the Study Quality Evaluation. These criteria are detailed in <i>Subsection E: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria of Section III: Systematic Literature Review Process</i> . For the synthesis, studies were grouped according to their publication type, as this supports the study risk of bias assessment described in Item 11.	III. E. INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted. The search was conducted across (1) IEEE Xplore, (2) ScienceDirect, (3) Scopus, and (4) Springer Link, complemented by snowballing from citation and multibase searching. The first search round was completed on September 16, 2025, and the final second round (snowballing) was completed on January 21, 2026	III. D. DATA SOURCES
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used. The search strategy was built from a PICOC-based conceptual structure and executed in Scopus, IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, and SpringerLink using Boolean operators for each data source that are detailed in <i>APPENDIX A. COMPLETE SEARCH</i>	APPENDIX A. COMPLETE SEARCH STRATEGY

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		<i>STRATEGY</i> , including the source name, the Boolean search query, the number of results obtained, as well as the search fields and filters applied based on the exclusion criteria, and the date of the search.	
Selection process	8	<p>Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.</p> <p>During study selection, records were assessed in two stages: an initial abstract/keywords screening for thematic relevance, followed by full-text screening using the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Three authors, Kelly Sangoluisa, Gino Auz, and Alison Betancourt, collaboratively conducted the screening and selection processes, they independently assessing each record and report to ensure methodological rigor. Disagreements were resolved through discussion; when consensus could not be reached, a fourth experienced reviewer was consulted to provide adjudication. As eligibility was limited to studies published in English and Spanish, no translation workflow was required; when methodological details were unclear, information was verified using full texts and supplementary materials. No automation tools were used. This process was detailed in <i>Subsection H: Study Selection and Figure 1. of the III: Systematic Literature Review Process</i>.</p>	III. H. STUDY SELECTION and FIGURE 1. Study selection process.
Data collection process	9	<p>Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.</p> <p>The information collected is detailed in <i>Subsection G: Data Extraction of III: Systematic Literature Review Process</i>. ATLAS.ti version 25.0.1.32924, was used to record and code the relevant information based on the NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0 and NIST AI Risk Management Framework (AI RMF) 1.0. Three authors, Kelly Sangoluisa, Gino Auz, and Alison Betancourt, collaboratively conducted the data extraction process, independently extracting data from each report to ensure methodological rigor. Disagreements were resolved through discussion; when consensus could not be reached, a fourth experienced reviewer was consulted to provide adjudication. No translation workflow was needed because only English and Spanish studies were eligible. No automation tool was used.</p>	III. G: Data Extraction
Data items	10a	<p>List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.</p> <p>Data were sought for prespecified outcome domains aligned with the review questions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Most relevant types of LLM applications in cybersecurity practice, referring to where and for what operational purpose LLMs were used (e.g., detection, response, governance), mapped to NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0 functions/categories and NIST AI Risk Management Framework (AI RMF) 1.0 - MAP 2 system categorization. (2) Most relevant technical challenges, including reliability limits, hallucinations, prompt-injection exposure, integration constraints, and operational stability issues. (3) Most relevant Ethical conflicts, including data sovereignty, privacy, transparency, accountability, and risks related to over-reliance on AI outputs; and (4) Most useful and relevant cybersecurity practices supported by LLM, which includes open source and commercial applications. <p>The timeframe of measurement corresponded to the publication/evaluation period of each study (2020-2025), and temporal patterns were analyzed by year when reported. For each included study, all results compatible with each outcome domain</p>	III: SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW PROCESS

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		were extracted from full texts and supplementary materials; no selective sampling of results within eligible domains was applied. For the interpretation of the review findings, all outcome domains were considered in alignment with the research questions, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of LLM applications, associated challenges and limitations, and their effectiveness and sustainability in real-world cybersecurity contexts.	
	10b	<p>List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.</p> <p>Using ATLAS.ti version 25.0.1.32924, co-occurrence matrices will be generated for all possible pair combinations of categories associated with the Govern, Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, and Recover functions of the NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0. This will identify the categories most frequently referenced by authors. Correspondence analysis will then be applied to these categories to determine the strongest relationships between them. This will identify related open-source and commercial LLM applications, prioritizing the LLM application selection process and demonstrating its usefulness for IT professionals in improving cybersecurity efforts. If the information is incomplete or unclear, no assumptions will be made to infer or complete the data.</p>	
Study risk of bias assessment	11	<p>Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.</p> <p>For the risk of bias in the included studies we employed two widely recognized evaluation tools, First, ROBIS (Risk of Bias in Systematic Reviews) focusing on 4 domains: 1. Study Eligibility Criteria, 2. Identification and Selection of Studies, 3. Data Collection and Study Appraisal, 4. Synthesis and Findings obtaining an Overall risk of bias</p> <p>Second, ROBINS-I (Risk of Bias in Non-Randomized Intervention Studies), focusing on confounding, selection of participants into the study, classification of interventions/exposures, deviations from intended interventions, missing data, measurement of outcomes, selection of the reported result obtaining an Overall risk of bias.</p> <p>Three authors, Kelly Sangoluisa, Gino Auz, and Alison Betancourt, collaboratively conducted the risk of bias assessment, independently evaluating each study to ensure methodological rigor. Disagreements were resolved through discussion; when consensus could not be reached, a fourth experienced reviewer was consulted to provide adjudication.</p> <p>This method is detailed in Subsection <i>F. STUDY QUALITY EVALUATION</i> of Section III: <i>Systematic Literature Review Process</i>. and APPENDIX B. COMPLETE ASSESSMENT OF RISK OF BIAS</p>	III. <i>F. STUDY QUALITY EVALUATION</i> , APPENDIX B. COMPLETE ASSESSMENT OF RISK OF BIAS
Effect measures	12	<p>Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results. Since the synthesis did not involve traditional quantitative meta-analysis, classic effect measures (e.g., risk ratio, mean difference) were not applied. Instead, exploratory multivariate techniques were employed:</p> <p>1) Co-occurrence analysis, quantified using absolute frequencies (positive whole counts of co-occurrences between codes).</p> <p>2) Simple correspondence analysis (CA), with Pearson-adjusted residuals to standardize observed-expected deviations and highlight significant relationships.</p> <p>Metrics included: total inertia, percentage of variance explained by dimensions (eigenvalues), absolute/relative contributions of categories, principal coordinates, and Pearson adjusted residuals (with thresholds to identify strong relationships). These measures allowed us to find the strongest relationships between all categories of the Govern, Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond and Recover functions of the NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0</p>	N/A
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	III. <i>H. STUDY SELECTION</i> , FIGURE 1. Study selection process

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	<p>To decide study eligibility for each synthesis, we applied a four-step process. First, records were screened using the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria (Item 5). Second, we made a study quality evaluation with two evaluation tools: ROBIS and ROBINS-I (Item 11), and only studies with low or moderate risk of bias were retained. Third, retained studies were coded based on NIST AI Risk Management Framework (AI RMF) 1.0 and NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0, all using ATLAS.ti version 25.0.1.32924. Fourth, final studies were assigned to each synthesis according to their relevant coding. Studies could contribute to more than one synthesis when relevant.</p> <p>This process is detailed in Subsection <i>H. STUDY SELECTION</i> of Section III: <i>Systematic Literature Review Process</i>. and FIGURE 1. Study selection process</p>	
13b	<p>Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.</p> <p>No statistical data conversions were required. Preparation focused on harmonizing extracted labels, standardizing thematic categories, and consolidating comparable findings across studies for narrative synthesis.</p>	N/A
13c	<p>Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.</p> <p>Results were tabulated using codebooks detailed in the APPENDIX C. CODEBOOKS USED FOR DATA EXTRACTION, where each study was coded under NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0 and NIST AI Risk Management Framework (AI RMF) 1.0 categories. Individual-study results were displayed with the aid of ATLAS.ti version 25.0.1.32924 filtering the codes.</p>	APPENDIX C. CODEBOOKS USED FOR DATA EXTRACTION
13d	<p>Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.</p> <p>Meta-analysis was not conducted due to methodological and reporting heterogeneity across included studies. Therefore, no fixed/random-effects models, heterogeneity estimators, or statistical pooling software were applied.</p> <p>To synthesize the results and justify the decisions, the functions (Govern, Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, and Recover from the NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0 and their corresponding categories identified in each study will be compared with the inclusion criteria. Studies without codable data for co-occurrences will be excluded. The results of each study will be tabulated in contingency matrices, exported from ATLAS.ti version 25.0.1.32924, with absolute co-occurrence frequencies (non-negative integers). For the synthesis, a simple correspondence analysis (CA) with Pearson adjusted residuals will be used to visualize the relationships through: Tables: Dim1 and Dim2, Adjusted Residuals (thresholds > 2 for significance), Visualization: Biplot of principal coordinates (Dim1 and Dim2, explaining >80\% of inertia) to determine the strongest relationships between categories of functions and obtain the most relevant open source and commercial LLM applications that cover these relationships in order to prioritize the mitigation of cybersecurity threats and incidents.</p>	N/A
13e	<p>Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).</p> <p>No analyses were conducted to explore possible causes of heterogeneity. No subgroup meta-analysis or meta-regression was performed.</p>	N/A

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	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results. A formal quantitative sensitivity analysis will be conducted. It is important to note that the entire set of 80 documents was coded by three researchers using ATLAS.ti version 25.0.1.32924. To assess intra-coder consistency, a random subsample of 15% of the documents (n = 12 of 80) will be independently recoded after a three-month separation period. This percentage falls within the 10% to 25% range typically recommended by O'Connor and Joffe (2020) for reliability checks in qualitative research.	III. I Coding reliability and robustness
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases). To assess risk of bias due to missing results in the synthesis (arising from reporting biases), we evaluated key sources: publication bias was minimized by not suppressing negative results; outcome reporting bias was addressed by including all outcomes from each study, regardless of favourability; time-lag bias was avoided by not delaying publication for unfavorable results. Statistical methods included correspondence analysis (CA) on all categories related to Govern, Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, and Recover functions of NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0, using symmetric normalization and Adjusted Pearson Residuals to detect data relations. Qualitative assessments used ROBIS or ROBINS-I (Item 11) for risk-of-bias evaluation in 80 articles.	APPENDIX B. COMPLETE ASSESSMENT OF RISK OF BIAS
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome. The level of confidence linked to the evidence articulated was not subjected to an exhaustive assessment, primarily due to the deliberate focus of this systematic review on the implementation of a descriptive qualitative analysis. Also was supported by inclusion and exclusion criteria, PRISMA reporting, and ROBIS or ROBINS-I Tool for quality evaluation.	III. E. INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA, APPENDIX B. COMPLETE ASSESSMENT OF RISK OF BIAS
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram. The search and selection process is illustrated in Figure 1. A total of 19,710 records were identified in databases and 45 through citation searches, and as a final result, the number of studies in the review was reduced to 80 after full text evaluation and exclusion based on eligibility criteria and risk of bias.	III.H) Study Selection, figure 1.
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded. In Figure 1, a total of 9 studies were excluded during the eligibility stage because they did not meet the predefined inclusion criteria (CI1–CI4) or met one or more exclusion criteria (CE1–CE3), as defined in Subsection III.E (Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria). Additionally, 7 studies identified through database searches and 15 studies identified through snowballing were assessed under the same eligibility criteria. Studies from both sources were either included or excluded based on their compliance with the defined inclusion (CI1–CI4) and exclusion criteria (CE1–CE3), as well as their quality assessment using the ROBINS-I and ROBIS tool.	Figure 1
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics. The appendix D contains each of the 80 included studies and presents their key characteristics, including authors, titles, publication identifiers, and years.	III.H) Study Selection. Appendix D, Table 5.

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Risk of bias in studies	18	<p>Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.</p> <p>The risk of bias assessments are presented in Appendix B. The appendix includes detailed tables reporting domain-level assessments and the overall risk of bias for each study, using the ROBIS tool and the ROBINS-I tool.</p>	III.H) Study Selection Appendix B
Results of individual studies	19	<p>For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.</p> <p>The results are presented as the frequency of references reported across the selected studies, based on the coding process of specific cybersecurity categories and NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0 functions using ATLAS.ti version 25.0.1.32924. For each of the 80 included studies, the key findings are summarized in Section IV, including the predominant LLM families, the corresponding cybersecurity domains, the identified technical and ethical challenges and the most relevant LLM applications.</p> <p>Additionally, the analysis is structured using two complementary frameworks: the NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0 and the NIST AI Risk Management Framework (AI RMF) 1.0, enabling the results to capture both cybersecurity operational functions and AI-related risk dimensions.</p> <p>The findings are presented through structured tables and figures, including Fig. 2 (temporal evolution of LLM applications), Fig. 3 (distribution of LLM families), Fig. 4 (applications across NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0 functions), Fig. 5 (technical challenges distribution), and Fig. 6 (ethical challenges distribution), as well as Tables 4–10, which summarize the correspondence analysis with the strongest relationships between categories from NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0 functions), the most relevant open source and commercial LLM applications related for each pair of categories that were identified in the reviewed studies, and in general the most relevant open source and commercial LLM applications for all categories.</p>	IV) Results.
Results of syntheses	20a	<p>For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.</p> <p>This section summarizes the characteristics of the 80 studies selected for the final analysis. All selected articles were published between 2023 and 2026. The reviewed studies cover a wide range of topics, including vulnerability detection, automated penetration testing, incident response, threat intelligence analysis, and phishing detection. In addition, several works explore the security risks associated with LLMs, such as their potential misuse for malware generation or exploitation tasks, as well as privacy and data protection concerns.</p> <p>All included studies passed the ROBINS-I quality assessment with a "low" or "moderate" risk of bias, ensuring the reliability of the primary studies. In parallel, the overall methodological quality of the systematic review process was assessed using the ROBIS tool, confirming a low risk of bias at the review level. A total of 22 studies were excluded due to a "severe" or "critical" risk of bias according to the ROBINS-I evaluation.</p>	IV) Results. III.H) Study Selection.
	20b	<p>Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.</p> <p>Given that this review followed a qualitative approach supported by figures and tables showing the distribution and frequency of the results, no statistical syntheses or meta-analyses were conducted, regarding the synthesis of the results, the functions (Govern, Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, and Recover) from the NIST Cybersecurity Framework 2.0 and their corresponding categories identified in each study were compared against the inclusion criteria and systematically coded, studies without</p>	IV) Results. Figures 2-6 Tables 4-8

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		<p>codable data for co-occurrences were excluded.</p> <p>The results of each study were tabulated in co-occurrence matrices, exported from ATLAS.ti version 25.0.1.32924, using absolute co-occurrence frequencies. Additionally, a simple correspondence analysis (CA) with Pearson adjusted residuals was performed. The relationships were visualized across 13 tables using Dimension 1 and Dimension 2, considering adjusted residual thresholds greater than 2 for statistical significance.</p> <p>This analysis enabled the identification of the 10 strongest relationships between function categories, leading to the determination of the most relevant open-source and commercial LLM applications that support these relationships and contribute to prioritizing the mitigation of cybersecurity threats and incidents.</p>	
	20c	<p>Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.</p> <p>No formal analysis was conducted to investigate the causes of differences between studies, causes of quantitative heterogeneity were not investigated (e.g., through subgroup analyses or meta-regression). However, some variations were observed across the results. These differences are mainly related to the type of cybersecurity application, the NIST function addressed, and the specific challenges reported in each study.</p>	IV) Results.
	20d	<p>Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.</p> <p>Cohen's kappa was calculated for each code category across the 12 documents, yielding $k=1.000$ for "Detect", "Govern", and "Protect", $k=0.625$ for "Identify", $k=0.438$ for "Recover" and $k=0.571$ for "Respond". The average kappa was 0.772 and the overall (global) kappa was 0.737, indicating substantial agreement. This stability check demonstrates high consistency in the coding process and confirms that the association structure obtained in the subsequent correspondence analysis is robust and not an artifact of subjective coding decisions.</p>	III. I Coding reliability and robustness
Reporting biases	21	<p>Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.</p> <p>This risk was minimized through the use of multiple databases and complementary snowballing strategies, which helped reduce the likelihood of missing relevant studies. No evaluations concerning the potential risk of bias due to absent results (reporting bias) were executed for any of the synthesized studies, as no statistical analyses of the research findings were undertaken. Therefore, the absent effect measures do not signify a bias concerning the outcomes of this review.</p>	III.F) Study Quality Evaluation III.H) Study Selection.
Certainty of evidence	22	<p>Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.</p> <p>The overall confidence in the findings is considered moderate, as only studies with low or moderate risk of bias were included. In addition, consistent patterns were observed across multiple studies, which supports the reliability of the results. No evaluation regarding the reliability of the evidence was provided for any if the outcomes (refer to item 15), since this systematic review concentrated solely on a qualitative descriptive analysis which excluded quantitative effect measures.</p>	IV) Results.
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	A general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence was added	V) Discussion
	23b	Limitations of the evidence and Threats of validity were included	V) Discussion- Limitations
	23c	Implications for Academia was added to the discussion section.	V) Discussion- Implications for Academia
	23d	Practical implications was added to the discussion section	V) Discussion- Practical Implications
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	The review was not registered	The review was not registered.

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	24b	No review protocol was prepared	Protocol was not published
	24c	Since there was no registry or protocol, there were no amendments to report.	N/A
Support	25	The author(s) received no specific funding for this work. <i>Section Acknowledgment</i>	
Competing interests	26	The authors have declared that no competing interests exist. <i>Section Acknowledgment</i>	
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	All supplementary information is available in Appendices section and some specific links to Zenodo repository	.

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